

DECO Activity Report

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D1.4: DECO Activity Report

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Acronyms

AEIDL: the European Association for Information on Local Development

CoP: Community of Practice

D: deliverable

DECO: dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

GI: Geographical Indications

KER: Key Exploitable Results

KPI: Key Performance Indicators

M: month

MAP: Multi-Actor Platform

MOVING: MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INTERconnectedness and Green growth

MRL: Mountain Reference Landscape

MRR: Mountain Reference Region

RP: reporting Period

RR: Reference Region

VC: value chain

WP: Work Package

Executive summary

The deliverable **D1.4 DECO Activity Report** is conceived as a self-assessment exercise that has the ultimate purpose of identifying improvements in the activities and tasks, making them the most appropriate to the needs of the project, based on the experiences of the activities implemented so far.

Focused on the development of the dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach (DECO) strategy (hereinafter the "Strategy") ([D1.1](#)), the D1.4 has two specific objectives:

- Analyse the performance of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities implemented by the project in years 1 and 2 towards achieving MOVING's objectives.
- Draw lessons, identify areas of improvements, and design actions and follow-up steps to be taken by the project so as to improve the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

D1.4 may lead to an Activity Report of the Strategy by assessing and reporting on all different channels, activities and products to maximise MOVING's impact.

This deliverable has been produced using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods for the analysis of the main MOVING communication channels and products. In this quantitative analysis, the external channels for outreach and the trainings and guidelines provided so far were also reviewed.

A survey among the project's partners, especially the Communication Task Force, was performed to complement the content analysis. A total of 23 responses from 21 partners have been received. The survey results have been used to collect information to better understand: a) how partners are using the communication channels and products of the project; b) in which areas they would need further support; c) what challenges they find to communicate about the project; etc.

To complement both the quantitative analysis and the survey, a workshop was held to provide a space for the MOVING Communication Task Force to discuss and collect ideas on how to improve communication and dissemination performance and impact.

The main results of the workshop have been used to produce the content in sections 4.5.3 Key Exploitable Results (KER), 4.6 Lessons learned and recommendations and 4.7 Review of the contingency plan within the DECO Strategy.

Section 4 of the deliverable on main communication activities and results, includes an overview of the status of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the DECO Strategy. For some of them, a new and more ambitious target in M48 has been set, given the good progress achieved so far of the initial targets.

Further in section 4, the deliverable analyses MOVING's communication channels, in particular the website, the Virtual Research Environment, the MOVING Community of Practice, the different social media accounts and the newsletter. Regarding MOVING's communication products, the

following have been evaluated: the visual identity of the project, news and blogs, policy briefs, videos and other products (press releases, infographics, brochures, etc.).

External channels for outreach have also been monitored. In particular, the focus has been on: (i) partners' communication and dissemination activities; (ii) link to other networks and projects; (iii) participation in third-party events; (iv) relation with press and media; and (v) publications and scientific journals.

The deliverable has considered the communication training and guideline provided so far and how partners value them, and has identified further training needs of the partners to improve their participation in dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach activities.

In section 4.5, the Exploitation Plan is developed as follows: introduction to this plan, objectives and Key Exploitable Results (KERs). It includes a table linking KER with lead partner from each work package (owner of KER); the description of the KER (including type of result) and the exploitation route(s) or potential use (commercial/industrial, academic, societal, policy).

Section 4.6 presents the lessons learned and recommendations drawn throughout the process of elaboration of this deliverable.

Finally, section 4.7 reviews the contingency plan within the DECO Strategy.

The deliverable includes three annexes: (i) detailed analysis of the survey results; (ii) categories used to classify MOVING's social media posts; and (iii) resources on communication evaluation used to inform this deliverable.

1. Introduction

MOVING (MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) is a Horizon 2020 project (2020-2024) coordinated by the University of Córdoba, gathering 23 partner organisations.

The project aims to build capacities and co-develop - in a bottom-up participatory process with value chain actors, stakeholders and policy-makers - relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of new or improved value chains (VCs) that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas in the face of climate and social changes.

MOVING project includes a Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy (hereafter the 'Strategy'; [D1.1](#)) that aims to facilitate the achievement of project objectives and support all its activities.

The objectives of the Strategy are connected through a four-step logic. Firstly, the Strategy focuses on the **discovery** of the project by the target audiences, and aims to build a coherent, unique and recognisable structure of MOVING so the audiences become acquainted with its goals and activities. Following this, the Strategy's main attention shifts to promoting the **engagement** of key stakeholders. Progressively it focuses on the **dissemination** of outcomes and results achieved, to finally address the enhancement of the project **legacy**, especially by facilitating the uptake of its outcomes and results within and beyond the project's scope.

Inputs derived from the monitoring of the Strategy will inform the project's internal reporting. Regular updates have been planned to allow the Strategy to evolve over time, as a result of new or emerging information, opportunities or trends.

The deliverable **D1.4 DECO Activity Report** was foreseen in M24 (August 2022) and it captures the activities implemented until in M1-M22 so as to be able to include the most up to date information. It is conceived as a self-assessment exercise that has the ultimate purpose of identifying improvements in the dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach activities and tasks tailoring them to the needs of the project, based on the experiences of the activities implemented so far.

The preparation of this deliverable includes the information and data presented in the periodic technical report for months 1-18 of the project (RP1). This self-assessment exercise will provide valuable inputs to prepare the periodic report related to the reporting period from month 19 to month 36 (RP2). The periodic technical report will detail the exploitation and dissemination of the results and if required an updated 'plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results'.

D1.4 may lead to an Activity Report of the Strategy by assessing and reporting on all different channels, activities and products to maximise MOVING impact. This task will be developed by the lead of WP1 (AEIDL) with the support of the project's coordinator, the Communication task force and the WPs leaders.

The monitoring and analysis of the DECO activities is an ongoing process in the project. In addition to the reporting periods, an update of the Strategy will be provided in the D1.6 DECO

Strategy foreseen in M42 and again a detailed progress report in deliverable D1.7 DECO Activity Report Year 3-4 in M48. Both deliverables will be publicly available.

2. Objectives

The DECO strategy is key to supporting MOVING in achieving its objectives. In this respect, it was designed to achieve the following specific objectives:

- SO.1 To raise awareness of project aims and activities (DISCOVERY)
- SO.2 To facilitate and promote engagement of partners, relevant actors and target audiences in the MAPs (ENGAGEMENT)
- SO.3 To inform about project outcomes and results and enable multipliers and the media to share relevant information (DISSEMINATION)
- SO.4 To facilitate the uptake of project outcomes and results within and beyond the scope of the project (LEGACY)

The Activity Report for years 1 and 2 (D1.4) aims to:

- Analyse the performance of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities implemented by the project in years 1 and 2 (M1-M22)¹ towards achieving the MOVING objectives.
- Draw lessons, identify areas of improvements, and design actions and follow-up steps to be taken by the project so to improve the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

3. Methodology

This report has been produced using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods for the analysis of the main MOVING communication channels and products. This analysis was based on information available from several sources including Google Analytics, Twitter Statistics, Meta Business Suite and LinkedIn and Instagram Analytics. In addition, an assessment was carried out to classify the content published in each communication channel. In this quantitative analysis, the external channels for outreach and the training and guideline provided so far were also reviewed.

A survey among the projects' partners, especially the Communication Task Force, – formed by at least one representative per MOVING partner - was performed to complement the content

¹ The delivery date for the D1.4 is M24 (end of August). In order to be able to carry out an information extraction and subsequent analysis, as well as to collect input from project partners through a survey and a workshop, the period that will be analysed is from M1 to M22 (end of June).

analysis. The survey was launched at the beginning of April 2022 and remained open for three weeks for partners to send their feedback. The survey is comprised of eight sections:

- Section 1: General information
- Section 2: MOVING communication and dissemination
- Section 3: MOVING communication channels
- Section 4: MOVING communication products
- Section 5: Partners' communication and dissemination actions
- Section 6: Trainings and guidelines
- Section 7: Key Exploitable Results (KER)
- Section 8: General remarks

A total of 23 responses from 21 partners have been received. The survey results have been used to collect information to better understand: a) how partners are using the communication channels and products of the project; b) in which areas they would need further support; c) what challenges they find to communicate about the project; etc.

To complement both the quantitative analysis and the survey, a workshop was held online on 1 June 2022. The event intended to provide a space for the MOVING Communication Task Force to discuss and collect ideas on how to improve communication and dissemination performance and impact. The workshop had 20 participants, with almost one representative from each of the MOVING consortium partners. The objectives of the workshop were to:

- Share experiences in the implementation of communication and dissemination activities during the first two years of the project;
- Provide an overview of the main results and statistics in relation to the implementation of communication and dissemination activities;
- Reflect collectively on what worked well and what needs to improve in the future;
- Identify the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and complete the information needed (owner of KER; description of the KER and exploitation route(s)/ potential use);
- Draw lessons and identify ways for improving the communication and dissemination activities during the second half of the project.

The workshop was structured around three main parts. The first part aimed at presenting the quantitative analysis and the results of the survey, as well as some examples of communication activities carried out by partners. The presentations were followed by group discussions on key topics.

In the second part, participants were divided into two break-out rooms to brainstorm and discuss ways for improving the communication and dissemination activities during the second half of the project based of the lessons learnt for their experience. In the third part, participants were asked to further develop the exploitation plan by completing the information needed for the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) already identified through the survey.

The main results of the workshop have been used to produce the content in sections 4.5.3 Key Exploitable Results (KER), 4.6 Lessons learned and recommendations and 4.7 Review of the contingency plan within the DECO Strategy.

4. Main communication activities and results

Since the start of the project in September 2020, the consortium has carried out numerous communication activities. The Deliverable 1.1 DECO Strategy, submitted in M6, describes all the communication and dissemination activities to be developed by project partners. Throughout this section, the different communication and dissemination activities indicated in D1.1 are described and analysed.

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) was defined in the Grant Agreement and the DECO Strategy (D1.1). Table 1 presents an overview of the status of the different materials compared to the KPIs outlined in the DECO Strategy. Overall, there is good progress made. For some of them, a new and more ambitious target for M48 has been set given the good progress achieved so far of the initial targets. One new indicator has also been added related to Instagram.

Table 1. Monitoring of Key Performance Indicators²

Key Communication Output	KPI	Target (M48)	Achievement (M22)	Updated target (M48)
Website	Number of downloads of documents from the MOVING website	2 000	1 459	2500
	Number of page views on MOVING website	50 000	28 871 Most viewed webpages are the homescreen, with (7 019 views), followed by the webpage presenting Reference regions (2 661), and the library of documents (1 425)	

² Data included in this table was extracted on 7 and 8 July 2022 from different sources as Google Analytics, META/Facebook Business Suite and Twitter Analytics.

	Number of unique visitors	5 000	4 512 (total number of active users) Total downloads done by 554 different users	7000
	Number of visits to the VC map & inventory	1 000	At the moment the number of views/visitors reflects those that viewed/downloaded/clicked on the deliverable 4.1 and the related infographic. The download figure will be provided at RP2.	
Social media	No of Twitter followers	1 000	604	
	No of LinkedIn followers	200	259	350
	No of Facebook followers	200	166	220
	No of Instagram followers	new	146	220
	No of Social Media impressions	25 000	220 611	300 000
	No of views in YouTube to the videos + webinars	2 000	1 318 views plus 111 extra views of videos currently unlisted or private because they were updated or modified	
Newsletter	Number of subscribers to the Newsletter	350	222	
Synergies	No of meetings from H2020 project in which MOVING participated	5	4	
MOVING App	No of download	200	App not yet developed	

Although the indicators related to the Community of Practice (CoP) are presented in deliverable D1.3 MOVING CoP design and implementation report, details of the scope of the materials produced by the CoP as well as their composition and participation in the activities can be found throughout this document (see section 4.1.3 of this report).

4.1. MOVING communication channels

4.1.1. Website

The MOVING website is the primary hub of information for the project, providing a ‘one-stop shop’ for resources, news, and key information on relevant initiatives. It links to and from the rest of communication and dissemination materials produced within the project.

Work on the website has been ongoing throughout the project, incorporating sections and content as soon as it becomes available and taking account arising needs.

A first version of the website was launched in November 2020, with a significant update occurring in February 2021 (current MOVING website). Regular improvements have been implemented since then, to better present the content and outputs of the project and make it more attractive to different stakeholders.

Since the launching of the full version of the website, a total of **5 508 users** have visited the MOVING website (target: 5 000). These numbers account for a total of **23 259 page views** (target: 50 000) since the beginning of the project. Hence, the website is showing good progress towards the targets set at the beginning of the project. Figure 1 shows an overview of the visits to the MOVING website.

Figure 1. Timeline of users visiting the Website between February 2021 and July 2022

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 7 July 2022

The flow of users has been quite stable during the development of the project. Some peaks can be observed in Figure 1. On 21 February 2022 (80 unique visitors), MOVING was celebrating a Steering Committee, on 24 December 2021 (61 unique visitors) the EU MAP was launched, and on 16 December 2021, MOVING held its first EU MAP webinar.

Apart from the homepage, the most popular web pages have been those presenting Reference Regions, the Library containing all the relevant documents, and the one for Work Packages &

Deliverables. Table 2 shows the most visited pages of the MOVING website in terms of total page views, total number of active users, views per user, and the average time of session (length of time users spend of each page).

Table 2. Overview of most visited MOVING webpages

	Views	Users	Views per user	Avg. eng. time
MOVING - Horizon 2020	7019	2358	2.92	1m 05s
Reference Regions	2661	812	2.99	0m 46s
Library	1425	474	3.15	0m 38s
Work Packages & Deliverables	1198	735	1.62	1m 01s
Partners	1032	610	1.7	0m 51s
What is MOVING	930	575	1.64	0m 43s
MOVING news	858	207	3.63	1m 02s
Events	816	208	3.97	1m 19s
What is the Community of Practice	605	358	1.73	0m 39s
MOVING blog	543	81	2.19	1m 22s

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 7 July 2022

There are several entry points to the website, i.e. organic search on engines (such as Google, Bing, Ecosia, etc.), direct entry by typing the URL³, redirection from social media, referrals from external websites, and RSS feed (other), which are shown in Figure 2.

³ Direct traffic accounts for users directly typing URLs on web browsers, but also for unknown referrals (e.g. link copied directly on an instant messaging applications such as WhatsApp or Facebook Messenger).

Figure 2. Entry points to the MOVING website.

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 7 July 2022

The most relevant entry point is through Organic search (i.e. Google) representing 42% of users. Regarding referrals (organic social), most came from social media such as Facebook (8% of total users), Twitter (7.5% of users) and LinkedIn (3%). And 1.41% of users came from Mailchimp (platform used to send the MOVING newsletter and event invitations).

Table 3 shows the country from which each unique user visited the MOVING website. Seven out of the first ten most popular countries are those from partners of the project and in which at least one Multi-Actor Platform is established.

Table 3. Users of the MOVING website sorted by country

No	Country	Users	Share
1	Italy	812	16.24%
2	Spain	697	13.94%
3	France	315	6.30%
4	United States	294	5.88%
5	Portugal	258	5.16%
6	United Kingdom	251	5.02%

7	Greece	247	4.94%
8	Switzerland	210	4.20%
9	Belgium	204	4.08%
10	Germany	167	3.34%

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 7 July 2022

Finally, according to Google Analytics, users have downloaded different PDF documents hosted on the website at least 1 459 times⁴ (target: **2 000**). With the progress made so far, it is expected to achieve the target set at the beginning of the project. Figure 3 presents the downloads of documents over the course of time, with peaks on specific dates corresponding to certain documents or information published: 21 February 2022 (51 downloads), individual policy briefs; 1 October 2021 (42 downloads), [D2.1](#) on Conceptual Analytical Framework; 3 February 2022 (40 downloads), [Highlights Report](#) of the first EU MAP webinar ; and 19 July 2021 (23 downloads), [D4.1](#) Inventory of Mountain Value Chains.

Figure 3. Overview of document downloads on the MOVING website

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 7 July 2022

⁴ Only downloads coming from the MOVING website are tracked by Google Analytics. Therefore, all downloads coming from different sources (social media, VRE, email, sharing among colleagues, etc.) are not counted as downloads.

4.1.2. The Virtual Research Environment

The MOVING VREs are built on the D4Science Infrastructure⁵ by exploiting the gCube open-source technology (Assante *et al.* 2019a, Assante *et al.* 2019b). From the end-user point of view, this is accessible via MOVING Gateway (<https://moving.d4science.org/>). The CNR (National Research Council) deploys and technically operates the VRE that support two-way communication with the members, exchanges, storage, social networking, activity trackers, and more functionalities.

Five VREs have been created as of June 2022 as shown in Figure 4. Two VREs are conceived to support the management of the project: Coordination Management and Project. The Regional MAPs VRE is used exclusively for the communication among the 23 regional MAPs' Coordination teams, while the EU Multi-Actor Platform VRE is open for stakeholders interested to exchange, learn and interact around the topic of resilience to climate change of mountain value chains.

Finally, the StoryMaps VRE is conceived to build and share Story Maps on mountain ecosystems and value chains from the 23 Reference Regions of the project.

Figure 4. MOVING VREs available in the MOVING Gateway

Source: MOVING H2020

⁵ D4Science Infrastructure: www.d4science.org

All VREs Labs (V Labs) include the following features:

- A **shared workspace** to enable every user to store and organise the information files he/she is interested in working with. In addition to that, the user is allowed to collaborate with other users by sharing objects and messages;
- A **user management facility** to enable authorised users (i.e., VLab Managers) to manage other users using or wanting to access the VLab. VLab Managers can (i) authorise users' access to the VLab, (ii) assign or withdraw roles to users, (iii) remove users, and (iv) send messages to the current users;
- A **social networking facility** to enable users to use the common facilities typical of social networks – e.g., posting, commenting – yet adapted to the settings of working environments like those characterising Blue-Cloud. Users can post news as well as applications;
- A **notification facility** to alert users on relevant activities. These notifications offer a sense of anticipation and create a productivity boost. Users receive an alert (through the selected channels, e.g., email, web portal, Twitter) notifying them when something of interest has happened in their VLab(s);
- A **members' facility** to provide users with a list of VLab co-workers, i.e., the list of members included in the VRE and contributing to it;
- A **messaging facility** to provide users with a cloud-based common email environment. The distinguishing feature is represented by its integration with the rest, e.g., it is possible to send any information file available in the workspace (regardless of how “big” and “complex” it may be) as an attachment without consuming bandwidth.

Additionally the StoryMaps VRE is equipped with an integrated tool (web application) capable of letting users build and share their Story Maps on mountain ecosystems and value chains. An example of two (parts of) Story maps can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Example of two Story Maps available in the StoryMaps VRE

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 6 presents the overall number of users benefitting from the facilities offered by the existing VREs. The five existing VREs Labs are serving more than 275 users. The detailed distribution of users on the VREs can be seen in Figure 7 and Table 4.

Figure 6. MOVING Gateway users

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 7. Users overview distributed by VRE

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 4. VRE dedicated Virtual Laboratories and number of members

VRE dedicated Labs	No. of members
1. Project	109
2. Coordination and management	16
3. Regional MAPs coordinators	61
4. EU MAP	48
5. Story maps	42

Figure 8 reports the overall number of working sessions initiated per month via the MOVING Gateway. Up to June 2022, a total of 10 146 working sessions have been launched by users, with

an average of 500 working sessions per month. Working session are connections or access to VREs.

Figure 8. MOVING Gateway working sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

The MOVING Gateway is also used as a repository of files that are managed in the common Workspace; a social space where messages can be posted to all members of one or more VREs Labs; a secure and confidential email system where users can exchange private messages with other registered users without knowing their private email addresses.

Figure 9 reports the overall workspace sessions initiated per month by the MOVING users. Workspace session are the connection/access to the MOVING Cloud repository of files (workspace). Figures 10 and 11 report the overall exploitation of the Social Interaction facilities.

Figure 9. MOVING VRE workspace sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 10. MOVING VRE Social Interaction posts

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 11. MOVING VRE Social Interaction likes

Source: MOVING H2020

In Figures 12 and 13, the geographical distribution of the users accessing the MOVING Gateway is reported. Figure 12 shows the European map coloured according to the average sessions duration expressed in seconds, while Figure 13 shows the map coloured according to the total number of page views.

Figure 12. Geographical distribution of the users accessing the MOVING Gateway - Sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 13. Geographical distribution of the users accessing the MOVING Gateway – Page views

Source: MOVING H2020

4.1.3. The MOVING Community of Practice

A core feature of the project is the creation and animation of a Community of Practice (CoP). The MOVING CoP is understood as a European-wide Science-Society-Policy interface to engage stakeholders around resilience to climate change, and other threats, of mountain value chains and bring together interested stakeholders to contribute to the co-creation and validation of all research outputs delivered by MOVING.

The MOVING CoP is the main forum for two-way peer exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge with different stakeholders (MOVING partners and externals to the project) and at different territorial level (regional and European). The conceptualisation of the MOVING CoP is transferred into practice through the creation of Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), that provide the space for interaction, exchange and learning with stakeholders of the community at all territorial levels (regional and European). Hence, MOVING has created, animated and facilitated 24 MAPs across Europe:

- [23 regional MAPs](#), established in the 23 Reference Regions; and
- [1 EU MAP](#).

Figure 14 represents graphically the structure of the CoP with different levels of interaction in the project.

Figure 14. Structure of the MOVING CoP

Source: MOVING H2020

Following the integrated transdisciplinary approach of the MOVING project, the MAPs provide a platform and space to engage with relevant stakeholders in the different activities of the project. This allows the exchange of knowledge and peer learning between stakeholders from the Reference Regions (RR) up to the European level.

Under WP1, AEIDL has developed a monitoring and evaluation tool for MAPs that helps to:

- keep track of and reflect on the performance and engagement of the MAPs.
- capture and record the needed information that feeds into deliverables and the reporting on the progress of the objectives achieved and measurable impacts of the project overall.

Regional MAPs

The 23 regional MAPs are established in the 23 Reference Regions covering 16 countries. These regions represent the wide diversity of mountain areas in Europe and neighbouring countries. Each of the regional MAPs are implemented, animated and facilitated by the coordinators of each Reference Region.

Figure 15. Distribution of MOVING Reference Regions

Source: MOVING H2020

During the first two years of the project the regional MAPs members have participated and developed the following activities:

- Task 3.3 Participatory Workshop on vulnerability analysis of land systems.
- Task 4.3 Extended value chain analysis.
- Task 4.4 Participatory workshops in each region.

The total number of members of the 23 regional MAPs is 766 stakeholders of which 69% are men and 31% are women. Figure 16 shows the distribution of the total number of members in different stakeholder categories. As can be seen, the most represented types of actors are: producers and producers associations; public authorities and policy makers; business from agriculture and researchers.

Figure 16. Regional MAPs' composition (type of actor, =766)

Source: MOVING H2020

The following figures show the total number of members of the regional MAPs by: a. (Figure 17) geographic area of influence (local or reference landscape, regional or reference region, national and other); b. (Figure 18) level of participation and involvement (core group, active participants and occasional or associated participants) and c. (Figure 19) age (under 25, 25 to 40 and over 40 years of age).

Figure 17. Regional MAPs' composition (area covered, =766)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 18. Regional MAPs' composition (level of participation, =766)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 19. Regional MAPs' composition (participants' age, = 766)

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 5 shows the main figures of regional MAPs activities in Year 1 and 2. It includes for tasks 3.3, 4.3 and 4.4 (both workshops and stakeholder consultations) the number of events organised, the number of participants and the number of stakeholders interviewed.

Table 5. Main figures of regional MAPs activities in Year 1 and 2

Task	Number of events	Number of participants	Number of stakeholders interviewed
Task 3.3 Participatory Workshop on vulnerability analysis of land systems	23	283	-
Task 3.3 Consultation of 8-10 experts, as well as local actors as farmers and forestry owners	23	-	290
Task 4.3 Extended value chain analysis	23	-	355
Task 4.4 Participatory Workshops in each region	21 ⁶	278	-
Other non-mandatory events (meetings, discussion groups, KoM, visits)	25	-	-
Total activities	115	561	645

⁶ The regional MAPs of the Austrian Alps (Austria) and Corsica (France) will carry out this task in the coming months.

EU MAP

The MOVING EU MAP offers an open space to stakeholders (from policy, research and relevant practice groups) that are interested to exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on resilience and sustainability of mountain value chains.

The total number of EU MAP members is 48 stakeholders, out of which 54% are women and 46% are men.

Figure 20. EU MAP composition (type of actor, =48)

Source: MOVING H2020

The main activities carried out by the EU MAP have been:

- Setting up the EU MAP

In order to set up a platform that will attend to the expectations and needs of the project, a survey was carried out and circulated among all MOVING partners in August 2021. The survey focused on collecting ideas, expectations and suggestions from partners and their potential regional MAP members (as some of the regional MAPs were still being formed). The results supported the definition of the scope of some EU MAP activities.

In addition, a stakeholders mapping exercise helped to identify external stakeholders, organisations and experts that might be interested in participating in the EU MAP, complementing and enriching the discussions. A total of 120 stakeholders were invited to join EU MAP and to participate in the first webinar.

Furthermore, a total of 6 interviews with key informants was carried out, giving valuable insights for the development of the EU MAP. The key informants were: Euromontana, Mountain Research Initiative (MRI) and GEO mountains, Mountains Partnership FAO, EU project Life MIDMACC, Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO) in Portugal) and the Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO). More information can be found in D1.3 MOVING CoP design and implementation report published in M24.

- Create and operationalise the VRE dedicated Lab.

The dedicated VRE Lab was launched in November 2021. On the MOVING website there is a specific [section](#) for the Community of Practice, and it links to the [EU MAP online platform](#).

- Organise the 1st webinar on “Mountain value chains: heterogeneity and Innovation”

MOVING held its [first EU MAP webinar](#) on Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation on 16 December 2021. The event gathered around 60 attendees from different backgrounds (research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.) from 18 countries.

The main objectives of this webinar were:

1. Present the MOVING project and promote the EU MAP;
2. Showcase specific traditional or emerging value chains working on innovation and resilience to climate change;
3. Enhance the exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on heterogeneity and innovation in mountain value chains.

During the webinar, two presentations focused on the first year of the project and its Community of Practice (CoP). Within the MOVING CoP, the EU MAP was presented. The event featured other presentations on mountain value chains of three [reference regions](#), which showed the heterogeneity and different levels of innovation: (i) Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham value chain; (ii) Speyside Malt Whisky value chain and (iii) Certified ecotourism Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains value chain.

All the [presentations](#) and [recordings](#) of the webinar are available on the [event page](#). The [highlights report](#) is available on the website and in [Zenodo](#).

- Other additional activities are compiled in the following table:

Table 6. EU MAP additional activities

Activity	Description	Timing
Contributions to open consultations and other processes	Contribution to the EU Roadmap restoring sustainable carbon cycles (news item and full contribution)	October 2021
	Contribution and support of Mountain Education and Innovation Manifesto (MEIM)	November 2021
	Brain drain – mitigating challenges associated with population decline (news item and full contribution)	June 2021
	Sustainable EU food system –new initiative	July 2021
Campaigns	Why an International Mountain Day?	December 2021
	A video was prepared for the International Mountain Day on 11 December 2021, MOVING Working in 23 Mountains Reference Regions and launched on Facebook with a total of 95 views and 330 people reached; and on Twitter with a total of 170 views and 793 impressions.	
	Women’s International Day The importance of women in the sustainability of mountain areas	March 2022
Infographics	International Mountain Day Retrospective	December 2021
	MOVING’s contribution to the EU Long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)	May 2021
Blog articles and news item	See all blog articles here and news item here . Also see section 4.2 MOVING communication products of this report.	Throughout years 1 and 2

Activity in the Virtual Research Environment

For the functioning of the EU MAP, relationships between the members need to be established by encouraging them to exchange knowledge and learn from each other. For that, a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is available on the MOVING Gateway starting from November 2021.

Project partners and external actors are able to join the EU MAP by filling in a specific [form](#), available on the dedicated website section for the [Community of Practice](#). The form complies with GDPR aspects regarding the use and management of personal data.

Figure 23, presents the total number of users that have joined the EU MAP on VRE. As of June 2022, the EU MAP VRE has nearly 50 users.

Figure 21. EU MAP VRE users

Source: MOVING H2020

Up to June 2022, more than 300 working sessions have been launched by users, with an average of 40 working sessions per month. The EU MAP VRE is also used as a social space where messages can be posted to all members.

4.1.4. Social media

MOVING’s social media accounts aim to increase awareness among users, while encouraging them to check and read the project’s outputs. Each social media channel is intended to reach a specific audience, and the messages are adapted accordingly. The content shared on each platform includes different types of outputs, usually directing traffic to the MOVING website. Social media acts as an accelerator of the discussion, triggering a snowball effect and enabling the project to reach beyond its ‘usual suspects’ audience.

Twitter

The MOVING Twitter account ([@MOVINGH2020](https://twitter.com/MOVINGH2020)) was created in September 2020, and was launched for the project’s Kick-off Meeting on 14-16 September 2020. It is the main corporate Twitter account of the project and it is managed in English. Other Twitter accounts have been set up to serve a more local audience, for example, the coordinator, UCO, has manages the account [@H2020Moving_UCO](https://twitter.com/H2020Moving_UCO) serving the audience in Spanish language and covering the three Reference Regions in Spain. The Communication Manager (AEIDL) manages the Twitter account, with contributions from the project partners. Figure 22 shows the distribution of MOVING

tweets by topic⁷. For this analysis, posts are classified according to the categories described in Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post.

Figure 22. MOVING Twitter posts by topic

Source: Own calculation through Twitter Insights, consulted on 7 July 2022

Out of the **194 tweets** published, the majority (around 58%) cover topics related to MOVING, while the rest are about contents by third parties. However, there was a large number of quoted tweets that dealt with other stakeholders or other projects.

It is important to note that in the first months of activity on Twitter, there were no MOVING results to share, so most of the activity referred to the category “Other stakeholders”, sharing content relevant to the theme of the project. Nonetheless, the indicated data shows a good balance among the categories analysed.

Regarding the format, tweets are usually accompanied by media assets to catch the users’ attention. This can include pictures, GIFs, links or videos. By the end of the period analysed (30 June 2022), the MOVING twitter account had **604 followers** (target: 1 000 followers). Figure 23 shows a clear increasing tendency in Twitter follows as illustrated by the green bars, which is expected to continue over the second half of the project. The orange line in the same figure shows the number of impressions reached by the Twitter posts in each month.

⁷ For this analysis, only posts originally created by MOVING have been taken into account. Retweets, quoted tweets or replies are discarded. In this sense, a total of 194 tweets were analysed.

Figure 23. Evolution of the No followers and impressions on MOVING's Twitter account

Source: Own calculations based on Twitter Analytics data consulted on 12 July 2022.

Facebook

The project's Facebook page was created and launched in September 2020. Since the beginning of the activity, there have been **142 posts**, plus several shares of content from third-party organisations. Figure 24 shows the type of content published on the MOVING Facebook page according to the categories included in Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING posts.

Figure 24. Distribution of MOVING posts in Facebook by category of content

Source: Own calculation based on Meta Business Suite data consulted on 7 July 2022.

Half of the posts (57%) cover topics strictly related to MOVING, while the remaining 44% is about contents produced by third parties (for example, webinars organised by European stakeholders, latest developments of other Horizon 2020 projects, or documents published by European Institutions that are of relevance to MOVING). It is important to note that, during the first months of the project, there were not many MOVING results to communicate about, so most of the activity referred to Other Stakeholders or Other EU projects. It is expected that, during the upcoming months, the MOVING-specific results will hold a bigger share, while still keeping a balance between project and third-party contents.

The posts published on the Facebook page include media to attract the users' attention, such as links, pictures or videos. Figure 25 shows the distribution of MOVING posts according to the type of media included with the posts. Facebook's algorithm often penalises posts that include external links. That is why posts that include images or video have a higher reach (impressions) than those that only include a link as a call to action (Figure 26).

Figure 25. Posts of Facebook page per content type

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

Figure 26. Average of reach, impressions and engaged users of Facebook posts per content type

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

By the end of the period analysed, the Facebook page had **178 followers** and 166 likes (initial target: 200). The new developments of Facebook pages indicate that ‘followers’ is a better number to track as these are users who may see the page’s updates and posts in their news feed. Users who liked the page automatically followed it as well, but with the new Facebook Pages Experience, those same users can unfollow the page and thus not see the page’s updates and posts in their newsfeed.

Figures 27 and 28 show the growth of followers and likes in the MOVING Facebook page.

Figure 27. Average performance over time of Facebook followers

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

Figure 28. Average performance over time of Facebook likes

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

Table 7, on the other hand, shows the country of origin of the Facebook followers. The Top10 countries correspond to a country where MOVING has established at least one Multi-Actor Platform, with the only exception of Belgium.

Table 7. Country of origin of MOVING Facebook followers

No	Country	Share
1	Italy	20.2%
2	Turkey	14.3%
3	Spain	13.1%
4	France	7.7%
5	Greece	6%
6	Romania	4.8%
7	Portugal	4.2%
8	Serbia	4.2%
9	Switzerland	3.6%
10	Belgium	3%

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

In order to increase the outreach of the project, MOVING has joined different groups related to rural development, youth, research and innovation, and Horizon 2020 projects. At the moment, the project is part of the following Facebook groups:

- Friends of ERP - European Rural Parliament. Created on 16 November 2016, it has now 461 members. The topics addressed by the group are about rural development, youth, digitalisation, climate change, smart villages, value chains, mountains and more.
- Horizon 2020, Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. Created on 8 July 2013, it has now 6418 members. The group posts about innovation, research, Horizon 2020, events, training, open calls, etc.

LinkedIn

MOVING has a company page on LinkedIn ([MOVING - Mountain Valorisation through Interconnectedness and Green Growth](#)) launched in September 2020. Since the beginning of the activity, there have been **117 posts**, plus several shares from third parties. Figure 29 shows the type of contents published on the MOVING LinkedIn page according to the categories included in Annex II. By the time of analysis, MOVING's LinkedIn company page had **259 followers** (target: 200).

Figure 29. Posts of LinkedIn page per content type

Source: LinkedIn Analytics, consulted on 17 July 2022

As on Facebook, MOVING has joined different groups related to rural development, sustainability and Horizon 2020 projects to bring the updates and results of the project to more people. At the moment, is part of the group Sustainable Agriculture & Rural Development.

The group was created in October 2012 and now has 13 705 members. Its aim is to create an international professional network favourable for exchanging information, knowledge, interaction (synergy) and capacity building on various aspects of rural development linked to MOVING interest: economic development, innovations in value chains (such as olive oil), bioeconomy, farmer organisations, land-use planning, food systems or climate change.

Instagram

The Instagram account was launched in August 2021. By the end of the period analysed, MOVING’s Instagram account had earned **145 followers**, through 64 posts and 19 stories. Figure 30 shows the type of contents published on Instagram according to the categories included in Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post.

Figure 30. Posts of Instagram page per content type

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

Table 8 shows the top 5 countries of origin of MOVING’s Instagram followers. All five of them correspond to countries where the project has established at least one Multi-Actor Platform.

Table 8. Country of origin of MOVING Instagram followers

No	Country	Share
1	Italy	21.6%
2	Spain	15.5%
3	Turkey	8.1%
4	France	6.8%
5	Portugal	6.1%

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 7 July 2022

Youtube

The MOVING YouTube account ([@MOVINGH2020](#)) was launched in March 2021. At the end of M22, the channel had 23 subscribers and 21 videos published. These videos accumulated 1 318 views plus 111 extra views of videos that are currently unpublished or private because they have been updated or modified. See section 4.2.5 of this report for more details.

4.1.5. Newsletter

The MOVING newsletter aims to communicate the developments of the project, as well as relevant information about other Horizon 2020 projects, European institutions or international organisations working on mountain value chains that may be interesting to the subscribers.

Two newsletters are sent out every year, usually in June and December. Therefore, in the first 24 months of the project, three newsletters have been published. The date of publishing is kept flexible, so it can be adapted to specific events or publications that might be of special relevance to the MOVING audience. In that case, newsletters may be earlier or later than the estimated date of publication. The decision is taken by the Communication Manager and the Project Coordinator.

The first MOVING Newsletter was sent in June 2021, and it was a first introduction to the project. It featured a leading article (interview to the MOVING Coordinator presenting the project), and news items regarding the first preliminary results and activities of the project. It also included news from external stakeholders relevant for the MOVING audience, and some future events.

The second newsletter was sent in December 2021, and its structure was updated to better introduce the contents of the project. It presented news about the project and its latest developments, a section regarding the latest activity of the MOVING Multi-Actor Platforms, a section of European news, and a section of other EU projects, where the latest development of some of the MOVING sister projects and other relevant initiatives is presented. It also featured upcoming events of interest to the audience. Third newsletter was sent on June 2022, and it followed the updated structure of the second issue.

The MOVING newsletter is managed by using Mailchimp, sent to a distribution list, shared through social media channels and then published on the dedicated webpage. Table 9 shows an overview of the three issues of the MOVING newsletters published so far. The 'opening rate' refers to the percentage of people subscribed to the mailing list that effectively open the newsletter. The 'click rate' refers to the percentage of hyperlinks included in the newsletter that were open by at least one reader.

Mailchimp tracks the interaction that subscribers have with the newsletter on the original email sent out by the platform, but the interaction achieved through other channels, such as social media, email forwards, or the MOVING website, cannot be measured. Therefore, the data shown in Table 9 should be understood as an underestimation of the actual data.

Table 9. Overview of MOVING newsletters

No.	Edition	Opening rate	Click rate	No. of subscribers
1	June 2021 edition	48%	26%	101
2	December 2021 edition	46.6%	23%	196
3	June 2022 edition	52.6%	19.5%	222

Source: Mailchimp, consulted on 30 June 2022

In addition to being sent to the MOVING mailing list, comprised of actors that have expressed their interest in being updated about the project development and compiling with GDPR, the newsletter is also shared on the project social media accounts, and stored on the website (<https://www.moving-h2020.eu/moving-newsletters/>). By the end of the period analysed, the newsletter had **222 subscribers**.

Figure 31. MOVING newsletter subscribers sorted by country

Source: Mailchimp, consulted on 8 July 2022

The majority of MOVING newsletter subscribers are from one of the countries where MOVING has a partner (Italy, Spain, Greece, and France, see Figure 31). Subscribers to the MOVING mailing list have different profiles, and represent several stakeholder categories. The majority of them (30%) come from research, and there is also a big representation of public authorities, stakeholder organisations and NGOs. There is no data available for one third of the subscribers, as no information was provided on their profile.

Figure 32. MOVING newsletter subscribers by category of stakeholders

Source: Mailchimp, consulted on 8 July 2022

4.2. MOVING communication products

MOVING has produced a wide range of communication and dissemination materials about its outcomes and results. Each communication product has a different layout and language according to the target audience it is meant to reach.

4.2.1. Visual identity of the project

By using a unique visual identity throughout the consortium and all our communications products, consistency is ensured in MOVING communications and dissemination. Templates for different types of documents (e.g. agenda, concept note, deliverable, PPT) were developed and shared with the Consortium.

Templates give a uniform image of the project and establish a visual language to indicate the information presented derives from the MOVING project. The MOVING visual identity complies with the visual guidelines of the European Commission.

The main elements of the visual identity package of MOVING comprise:

1. Logo, in several applications and formats (vertical and horizontal applications, coloured and black and white versions);
2. Graphic Charter, including the corporate colours and typographies to be used in the MOVING communication materials;
3. Template package, including templates for presentations, deliverables, agenda, working documents, and event communications. All of these templates include the EU logo and disclaimer, and are updated when needed (e.g. a partner changes their visual identity).
4. The project roll-ups have been designed in English and translated into three languages.

All of these elements are available in the project VRE for partners to use.

4.2.2. News

The website's [news section](#) is key to keeping interested parties up to date, generating traffic to the site and retaining the audience. The information provided is on the results of the project, on the latest news in rural policy, and on events that MOVING has attended or organised. Overall, MOVING has published a total of 59 news (some of them under more than one category), which are filtered as follows:

Table 10. News item in year 1 and 2

Category	Number of news	Topics
MOVING	33	Mountains, value chains, multi-actor platform, vulnerability, reference region, climate change, meeting, mountain products, policy brief, youth, foresight, agriculture.
EU institutions	11	Rural development, land abandonment, climate change, agriculture, Cohesion Policy, climate action, forest, biodiversity, youth.
European stakeholders	8	Geographical indications, mountain products, innovation, youth, climate action, good practices, value chains, climate change, forest, mountains, Cohesion Policy.
International organisations	6	Mountains, sustainability, mountain products, climate change.

H2020 projects	3	Rural development, sustainability, value chains.
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Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.3. Blogs

Overall, there are 24 blogs posts published, 8 written by European stakeholders and 16, by MOVING partners.

Most popular blog posts in the analysed period are:

1. [The revision of the EU Geographical Indications system](#) (189 views)
2. [Linking the Value Chain to Socio-Ecological Systems approaches](#) (121 views)
3. [Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation patterns](#) (105 views)

The MOVING blog posts aim to explain the project’s progress, disseminate results, share partners’ knowledge on project-related matters and stimulate innovation in mountain value chains.

For example to facilitate the understanding of the Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF) [D2.1](#) were developed an [explanatory video](#) and a [blog article](#) titled “Linking the Value Chain to Socio-Ecological Systems approaches”.

The blog posts from other institutions, organisations and projects represent a communication product that facilitates the creation of alliances, exchange knowledge, and engage the main actors and stakeholders of MOVING’s Community of Practice. For instance, MOVING has developed various blog posts and interviews with experts from the Labex ITTEM, University of Milan (UNIMONT), Montana 174 project (Euromontana), the Institute for Alpine Environment (Eurac Research), Mountain Partnership, Scalable project and the University of Innsbruck.

The [blog](#) article written by Francesca Alampi from AREPO, one of the MOVING partners, on the revision of the EU Geographical Indications (GI) system explained in detail the [proposal for a regulation on the revision of the EU GI system](#) and the implications for mountain products published by the European Commission (EC). This blog was the basis for the preparation of the second EU MAP webinar that is foreseen in November 2022.

Table 11. Blogs post in year 1 and 2

Blog articles/posts	Publishing date
The revision of the EU Geographical Indications system	May 2022
New mountain professionals on the way!	May 2022
Developing a virtual student community – MSc Sustainable Mountain Development	April 2022

Get to know the project SCALABLE	March 2022
Consequences of the transformation of agricultural landscapes on ecosystem services in the European Alps	February 2022
How does the Cohesion Policy influence mountains?	January 2022
Governance in mountain areas: what has changed in the last years?	November 2021
Getting to know Labex ITTEM: mountain research programme in Human and Social Sciences	November 2021
Face-to-face workshop on the value chain of the Iberian Ham PDO Los Pedroches	June 2022
MOVING contributes to the EU long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)	June 2022
The revision of the EU Geographical Indications system	May 2022
MOVING: Meeting of the key stakeholders of the organic mountain olive oil value chain	May 2022
Innovative and sustainable tourism in mountains regions	April 2022
MOVING's first year and a half	March 2022
The importance of women in the sustainability of mountain areas	March 2022
Building synergies with local actors in Los Pedroches	February 2022
Work progress in the MOVING's Swiss Alps Reference Region	January 2022
Vulnerability analysis at the Central Apennines mountain reference region	November 2021
Linking the Value Chain to Socio-Ecological Systems approaches	November 2021
MOVING's participation in the Forum Origin, Diversity and Territories	October 2021
Vulnerability analysis in the Betic Systems of Spain	October 2021
Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation patterns	June 2021
Land use systems in MOVING Reference Region	June 2021
Setting the scene for MOVING	June 2021

Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.4. Policy Briefs

The [Initial set of Policy briefs](#) (D2.2, lead University of Pisa) was published in August 2021. The briefs were compiled building on the information collected in WP4, task 4.1 “Inventory of Mountain Value Chains”, and through consultation with the regional Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) in each case-study region.

The Policy briefs include the description of the Mountain Reference Region (MRR), the value chain (VC) contribution to sustainability and resilience of the region, some innovation components of the VC, and a number of policy considerations.

AEIDL prepared an attractive format for the 23 individual documents to facilitate communication and dissemination at reference region level. The individual documents were available on the website in February 2022. See related [news item](#) included in the [newsletter of June 2022](#).

MOVING First Set of Policy Briefs

one for each of the 23 Reference Regions

The documents have been widely promoted through social media. On Twitter, the posts (on [21 February](#) and on [4 April](#)) have reached 2584 impressions and 19 retweets. The post was retweeted by Euromontana and quoted by Mountain Partnership.

On LinkedIn, the [post](#) had 164 impressions and was shared 4 times. On Facebook, the [post](#) had 201 people reached.

4.2.5. Videos

So far, 21 videos have been produced by MOVING and uploaded to the project's [YouTube channel](#). The videos are categorised into four playlists (community, results, EU MAP webinar and partners) totaling 1318 views.

Table 12. MOVING videos and playlists

Playlist	Videos
Community	<p>The MOVING video, which presents the project, its objectives and invites people to join the community, has been translated into 11 languages. They have a total of 1044 views.</p> <p>The video MOVING Know the 23 Mountains Reference Regions and its Value Chains shows the location of the 23 Reference Regions and displays a picture and the value chain of each of them. It has a total of 48 views.</p>
Results	<p>Understanding MOVING Conceptual and Analytical Framework. This video facilitates the comprehension of deliverable D2.1. It has a total of 121 views.</p>

	Understanding MOVING Participatory multi-level foresight exercises . This video explains the work to be carried out by work package 6 in the second half of the project. It has a total of 38 views.
EU MAP webinar	The five videos of the EU MAP webinar on Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation has a total of 127 views. They were focused on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOVING: first year of progress and results • MOVING Community of Practice and the EU Multi-Actor Platform • Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham value chain • Speyside Malt Whisky value chain • Certified ecotourism Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains value chain
Partners	A total of six videos have been facilitated by partners from different RRs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sierra Morena (coordinated by University of Cordoba): (i) MOVING at European Researchers' Night; (ii) MOVING and its work in mountain value chains and (iii) Importance of the production system of a value chain. • UK-Scotland (coordinated by The James Hutton Institute): (i) Why mountains matter and (ii) MOVING Speyside Whisky Value Chain research summary • Swiss Alps (coordinated by ZHAW) presented in an ORIGIN event: Swiss Alps Reference Region.

Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.6. Other products

MOVING has produced several other communication materials. In the beginning of the project a [press release](#) was published and a [leaflet](#) (online version) was produced in 12 languages (Czech, Serbian, Slovak, French, Spanish, English, Hungarian, Romanian, Turkish, Portuguese, Italian and Greek). All are available in the website's [Library](#).

MOVING has also produced four infographics:

- [Mountains Value Chains Inventory](#) (September 2021) related to D4.1 Inventory of Mountain Value Chains.
- [International Mountain Day | Retrospective](#) (December 2021) related to D4.2 List of selected value chains and relationship building.
- [MOVING 23 selected Value Chains](#) (February 2022)
- [MOVING's contribution to the EU Long-term vision for rural areas \(LTVRA\)](#) (May 2022)

MOVING has also produced banners and animated pictures (GIF) for the website and social media management, as well as a [poster](#) in April 2022 to raise awareness on the project, the 23 RRs, the concept and approach, the CoP, the objectives, impacts and partners. It is available in power point format for partners to adapt to their scientific posters.

4.3. External channels for outreach

4.3.1. Partners' communication channels and activities

In addition to the MOVING Communication channels, the consortium partners promote the project through their own communication channels, networks and organisations. Based on the survey results (see Annex I), the main communication channels used by partners were the “Workshops and events organised by my organisation” (64%), “Email” (59%) and “Social Media accounts of my organisation” (45.5%).

Regarding communication and dissemination actions undertaken by partners, more than 60% (total responses=23) answered to be carrying out the following actions:

- Share the deliverables, infographics, policy briefs, videos, leaflets, and other relevant outputs produced by the project with my contacts (via email, social media, etc.) (74% of respondents).
- Translate specific outputs from the project to facilitate dissemination in my country (65% of respondents).
- Retweet or share the posts from MOVING social media accounts with my personal accounts / the accounts of my institution (61% of respondents).

4.3.2. Link to other networks and projects

The project's website includes a [dedicated webpage for networking](#) (including other H2020 projects and other projects, European Institutions and Agencies, European organisations and international organisations).

MOVING also relies on the communication channels of several European and international organisations and networks, which act as multipliers and contribute to disseminating the project's key messages and outputs.

MOVING is part of the cluster of the Rural Renaissance call (RUR-01 and RUR-02) together with SHERPA, DESIRA, RURALIZATION and POLIRURAL. The cluster aims to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between the projects, building on each other's activities, and boosting the communication and dissemination of outcomes, contributing to the future rural policies.

Some of the activities realised within this Rural Cluster have led to MOVING articles and updates published in newsletters and websites of [SHERPA](#), [DESIRA](#) or [POLIRURAL](#).

In addition to coordination meetings among the cluster projects, several events have been organised where MOVING has been an active part:

- On 2 December 2021, MOVING participated in the [SHERPA webinar](#) Beyond the policy brief: how to engage local actors in the policy process. The project coordinator, Mar Delgado [presented](#) the MOVING CoP.
- On 31 January and 1 February 2022, SHERPA project had its annual conference. In the group discussion on 'Farm diversification and food chains', Sherman Farhad [presented](#) how the MOVING project contributes to the establishment of upscaled Value Chains and to the long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA).
- On 15 June, MOVING, SHERPA and DESIRA organised a [special session](#) on Science-policy-society interfaces for resilient and sustainable rural development in the European Society for Ecological Economics (ESEE) 2022 Congress.

Different content and posts on social media have been shared by organisations and institutions such as: [UNESCO Man and Biosphere](#), [EESC Agriculture Rural Development and Fisheries](#), [DG REGIO Regional & Urban Policy department of the EC](#), European Parliament [Intergroup RUMRA](#); the [European Network for Rural Development](#) (ENRD), [Euromontana](#), [Mountain Partnership](#), [Mountain research Initiative](#), [Mountain Biodiversity](#), [EURAC Research](#), the [Centre for Mountain Studies at Perth College UHI](#), [UniMont](#), [Mountain Forum](#), [Adaptation at Altitude](#), [Europe Direct Pyrenees](#), [Labex ITTEM](#) as well as National Rural Networks specially from Spain, Portugal and Romania.

In the framework of the Mountain Education and Innovation Manifesto, MOVING participated in the "Youth4Mountains" webinar series (see full [report](#)).

4.3.3. Participation in third party events

Partners have participated in several external events to present the project and its results to external audiences. According to the data reported in the internal tool for monitoring communication and dissemination activities, MOVING has been presented in 28 external events. These have been classified according to the categories used by the European Commission in the Funding and Tenders Portal. Figure 33 shows the type of events MOVING partners have participated in, while Figure 34 shows the area of influence of the events attended.

Figure 33. Type of events attended by MOVING partners communicating and disseminating results and findings of the project.

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 34. Area of influence of the events attended by MOVING partners.

Source: MOVING H2020

Out of the total number of events, 16 were held online, while the rest (12) took place face-to-face. Concerning type of participation, all events included an oral presentation or talk about the results and findings of the project.

4.3.4. Relation with press and media

Media are a great way to improve the visibility of MOVING. Partners are encouraged to try to publish via these channels to communicate to regional or national audiences about the project, its results and the Multi-Actor Platforms – as well as the funding received from the EC and the Horizon 2020 programme. In total, **197 actions** have been carried out by partners during years 1 and 2. The figures below showcase the main types of actions and the level at which these actions have been coordinated (area of influence).

Source: MOVING H2020

Notable to mention the high number of ‘website’ category. About 80% of these refer to online information and news websites at national, regional and local levels. The remaining ones are partners’ own websites and other organisations (i.e. FAO).

Figure 36. Area of influence of the media actions undertaken by MOVING partners.

Source: MOVING H2020

These are a few examples of actions carried out by project partners in an effort to disseminate and raise awareness of MOVING through the various channels available to them.

- University of Córdoba, as coordinator of the project, has established regular links with local and regional media channels, such as [news articles](#) or [radio interviews](#).
- University of Molise has managed to have a [news segment](#) and interview in the regional TV station of Rai (Italian news station).
- The Region of Crete has good and established connections with local and regional media. Their [press releases](#) are usually picked up by many online news and blog websites.

4.3.5. Publications and scientific journals

During the first half of the project there have been no approved scientific publications. As the project develops, more scientific publications are expected during the second half of MOVING.

4.4. Communication training and guideline

A Communication Task Force was established, in the first months of the project, to ensure a better coordination of the project's communication effort and increase its outreach throughout both the project and partner organisations' channels and network. It brings together one contact person per organisation of the consortium.

This taskforce had two online meetings to establish the principles for collaboration and activities to be undertaken. On December 2021, a specific session was organised to facilitate the understanding of communication and dissemination channels, products and activities, as well as possible complementarities and multiplier effect. The potential of the project's Community of Practice to contribute to the project's objectives was also discussed.

AEIDL produced a set of communication guidelines that contain information on the Communication Task Force, the language and writing style, use of social media, blog posts, press releases, use of EU acknowledgement and disclaimer, and the monitoring tool for communication and dissemination activities.

4.5. Exploitation Plan

The exploitation plan constitutes the exploitation strategy during the project lifetime. The outline for the future exploitation plan is divided into five chapters:

1. Introduction
2. Objectives
3. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)
4. Exploitation Strategy
5. Conclusions and next steps

To this end, from M18 a MOVING exploitation plan is being proposed and developed to update the information included in the DECO strategy.

4.5.1. Introduction

In MOVING, exploitation revolves around getting stakeholders to effectively use the developed tools. MOVING results have a strong public nature. The methodologies and tools developed during MOVING will be made fully available to potential users through toolkits. AEIDL (WP1 Leader) and the Communications Task Force will coordinate the exploitation activities.

While dissemination of MOVING's knowledge and progress will be important to raise awareness of the project's tools and results, this alone will not guarantee the maximum possible long-term

impact of the project's work. Therefore, concrete actions will be taken to ensure that end-users take advantage of and use the results and tools developed to achieve the project's objectives.

In response to this, an exploitation plan is being drawn up which includes five chapters. See the detail of the outline in Table 13.

Table 13. Exploitation Plan outline on making use of MOVING results and tools beyond the project

Timeline	Chapter of the MOVING exploitation plan
To be developed before M24 under D1.4	<p>1. Introduction</p> <p>2. Objectives of the plan <i>This section will include the goal and specific objectives of this exploitation plan.</i></p>
To be developed before M24 under D1.4 and revisited before M36	<p>3. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) <i>This will include a table linking KER with lead partner in brackets-WP (owner of KER); Description of the KER (including type of results); exploitation route(s)/ potential use (commercial/industrial, academic, societal, policy)</i></p>
To be developed for M36 second reporting period	<p>4. Exploitation strategy This section will include:</p> <p>4.1 Potential users-audience Including geographical coverage and multipliers</p> <p>4.2 Exploitation mechanisms</p> <p>4.2.1 Joint exploitation activities</p> <p>4.2.1.1 Exploitation activities for MOVING Value Chains</p> <p>4.2.1.2 Exploitation activities for MOVING Packaging methodological guidelines and capacities</p> <p>4.2.1.3 Exploitation activities for the MOVING Policy Toolkit</p> <p>4.2.1.4 Exploitation activities for the MOVING Community of Practice</p> <p>4.2.1.5 Exploitation activities for (to be added)</p> <p>4.2.2 Individual exploitation plans</p> <p>4.3 Monitoring and evaluation: KPI</p> <p>4.4 Exploitation barriers</p> <p>4.5 Intellectual Property</p> <p>5. Conclusions and next steps</p>

Source: MOVING H2020

The key concepts of the exploitation plan are:

- **Result:** Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.
- **Exploitation:** the use of results for commercial purposes, further research, education, or in public policymaking.
- **Exploitation route(s)/ potential use:** commercial/industrial, academic, societal and policy.
- **Key Exploitable Result (KER):** an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

There are three **main areas of work** in which exploitation action will focus on:

- Value Chains valorisation
- Packaging methodological guidelines and capacities
- Policy toolkit

The KERs and the activities to effectively guarantee their uptake by end-users, have been identified and defined in the dedicated workshops to prepare D1.4.

An updated version of the exploitation plan will be finalised before M36 (chapters 4 and 5) and its results will be included in the Periodic Report of M36. It will include an update of chapter 3 on Identification of KERs. Work will continue on this plan in the development of D1.6 and D1.7 as well as in the different reporting periods. External actors involved in the CoP could also be asked to identify possible synergies and build on the results of MOVING.

4.5.2. Objectives of the exploitation plan

The main goal of the exploitation plan is to make use of the results of the project towards the end of the project and beyond. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the main exploitable results, who is the owner and what the exploitation route will be;
2. Analyse the commitments and responsibilities of the project partners in the exploitation activities to be carried out;
3. Define the objectives and expected added value for the main stakeholders/target audience/end-user of the exploitable results;
4. Present an overview of how the exploitable results will be used by key stakeholders;
5. Ensure a sustainable impact of the project after the end of the funding period.

4.5.3. Key Exploitable Results

Table 14 shows a list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that build on the key MOVING communication outputs described in the DECO strategy (D1.1). The information has been completed by partners, especially WPs and task leaders.

Table 14. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

KER	Lead partner (owner of KER)	Description of the KER and type of result	Exploitation route(s)/ potential use			
			Commercial/Industrial	Academic	Societal	Policy
D2.1 Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF)	University of Pisa	The CAF defines and elaborates on the key concepts of the project i.e. Socio-ecological systems, value chains, social practices, assemblages, telecoupling, resilience or sustainability.		The CAF can provide a new tool for analyse the contribution of value chains to the resilience and sustainability of mountain and other marginal areas.		
D2.2 Initial set of Policy briefs	University of Pisa	The set comprises 23 Policy Briefs describing for case-study value chain a the key potential contributions of value chain to the resilience and sustainable development of the related Mountain Reference Region (MRR).				The Policy briefs provide information on the critical issues policies at all scales (EU, regional, and local) must account for to foster the value chain contribution to the resilience, sustainability, and

						development of the MRR.
D2.3 Final Conceptual framework	University of Pisa	The final CAF will document the conceptual pathway undergone along with the project, showing how the initial set of concepts have evolved on the basis of the participatory empirical work.		The final CAF will provide the basis for key project messages contributing to the advancement of theoretical knowledge in the field.		
D2.4 Final set of Policy Briefs	University of Pisa	The final set of Policy Briefs will summarise the key messages as the main results of the project in each MRR. It will provide policy recommendations to foster resilience and sustainability in each MRR. Moreover, an additional Policy Brief will be dedicated to synthesise the main messages on the final CAF.		One Policy Brief will report the main messages from the final CAF.		The final set of Policy briefs will collect the main project's results and provide place-based policy recommendations to foster resilience and sustainable development in each MRR.
D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions	University of Évora	D3.1 characterises the farming and forestry systems existing in the 23 Mountain Reference Regions, as well as their dynamics, based on existing spatially explicit assessments at global, European and regional scales.		The characterisation of the main archetypes, in the context of the studied Mountain Reference Regions, may allow the establishment of linkages between the region-specific land use systems and expected changes driven by new large-scale environmental		D3.1 illustrates the diversity of farming and forestry systems in Mountain Reference Regions.

				conditions, and also improve the transferability of place-based research to understand processes of change in similar areas.		
D3.2 Land use systems and vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions	University of Cordoba	D3.2 identifies, in a participatory way, the vulnerability to key drivers of change of the 23 land use systems representing a wide diversity of European mountain regions.	Individual findings of interest to the relevant businesses and sectors (in MRL but also other similar enterprises in mountain areas). Potential exploitation route could be interactive visual tools, specially maps and indicators.	It provides a comparative analysis of vulnerability of diverse land use systems in the 23 European MRLs.	Short briefing or other product on how the land use system in each of the MRLs/MRRs might be vulnerable to climate change and other drivers, and what is recommended to reduce the negative impacts.	D3.2 could be useful to illustrate the diversity of land use systems in European mountain regions, and how climate change and other drivers may affect them in different ways, and how therefore, they require different policy designs.
D3.3 Tools for science-society-policy interfaces	CNR	The Virtual Research Environments constitute a data and information exchange platform that foster collaboration and communication between the project members and the stakeholder community. The Story Map Building and Visualising tool allows describing value chains and regional concepts that overall contribute to	The Story Map Building and Visualising Tool allows disseminating value chain information to the large public in a more effective and interactive way than traditional approaches. This technology is valuable to reach	Story Maps contribute to building a shared and overall knowledge about European value chains, from which new knowledge can be inferred, thanks to the use of edge Semantic technology.	The tool informs the large public and the MOVING stakeholders about the value chains and supports decision-making. It targets the realisation of a friendly spatial view to explore stakeholders' information and easy-to-read story maps and "Science	Understanding a territory as a whole is integral to creating sustainability policy and intervene on the aspects that negatively affect the value chains.

		describe a territory beyond its map.	industrial partners and possibly attract funds on the value chains.		Digests” about mountain areas’ vulnerability and value chains.	
D4.1 Inventory of Mountain value chains	University of Pisa	The inventory collects the descriptions of more than 400 value chains located in EU mountain areas. In the inventory, each value chain is described together with its related natural resource systems. Moreover, D4.1 collects an indication of the level of innovation within each value chains.		D4.1 could be useful to illustrate the range of value chains in European Mountains.		D4.1 could be useful to illustrate the range of value chains in European Mountains.
D4.2 List of selected value-chains and relationship building	The James Hutton Institute	The list identifies the 23 MRL value chains and the main actors that could be involved in the participatory value chain analyses.		Together with the D4.1, could be useful to illustrate the range of value chains and actors involved in European Mountains, including the importance of products and actors that are not traditionally associated with mountain farming, forestry or fisheries.	Information on the diversity of mountain value chains in their regions - exploitation has already taken place via provision of infographic (1, 2) and MRR/MRL webpages .	Together with the D4.1, could be useful to illustrate the range of value chains and actors involved in European Mountains, including the importance of products and actors that are not traditionally associated with mountain farming, forestry or fisheries. Relevant for the understanding of LTVRA and the functions of

						mountain economies.
D4.4 Digital stories from each reference region	CZU	D4.4 will generate digital 'story maps'.		D4.4 will provide an overview of important issues related to the mountain VC's in Europe that can serve as an inspiration for further academic work.	D4.4 will provide a concise summary of each region, studies VC, important actors and key issues related to sustainability and resilience.	
D4.5 Report on Vulnerability and Resilience Performance of 23 Reference Region Value Chains	The James Hutton Institute	D4.5 will identify the vulnerabilities and resilience of the VC in 23 MRL (not MRRs) to illustrate whether VC need to be more sustainable or resilient		Findings on similarities or differences in types of resilience/vulnerabilities could be developed into a scientific paper		Findings on similarities or differences in types of vulnerability/resilience could be developed into a briefing for EC DG Agri, DG Env and DG Clima.
D4.6 Global Upgrading Strategy	The James Hutton Institute	D4.6 will identify what changes are recommended by the MRL MAPs to improve the performance of the VC in terms of supporting mountain rural development	Individual findings of interest to the relevant businesses and sectors (in that MRL but also other similar enterprises in mountain areas). Potential exploitation route - infographic or briefing per cluster (meat, dairy, crops, alcohol) or VC promoted to	Findings on similarities or differences in types of resilience/vulnerabilities could be developed into a scientific paper	Short briefing or other product on how their MRL/MRR might be vulnerable (or resilient) and what is recommended to improve or sustain the current trend	Findings on similarities or differences in types of solutions could be developed into a briefing for EC DG Agri, DG Env and DG Clima.

			commercial organisations via social media, also through dissemination to the local MAPs			
D4.7 31 Practice Abstracts	CZU	D4.7 will identify key issues for each case study region and implications for practitioners and other end-users	Information about main results and outcomes of the project, main practical recommendations	Information about main results and outcomes of the project	Information about main results and outcomes of the project	Information about main results and outcomes of the project, main recommendations for policy makers
D5.1 Comparative cross-case report on Mountain value chains	University of Cordoba	D5.1 will identify (five - TBC) key clusters of VCs within European MRRs.		Findings on similarities or differences in types of resilience/vulnerabilities of the different clusters of VCs could be developed into a scientific paper.	Short briefing or other product on how each of the clusters of VCs might be vulnerable (or resilient).	Each cluster will draft a policy brief to raise awareness about the goods and services provided by MRRs and to guide evidence-based solutions.
D5.2 Policy Briefs	University of Cordoba	This set comprises 5 Policy Briefs corresponding to each of the 5 clusters of VCs (to be defined). They aim to communicate the main outcomes of each of the clusters and to raise awareness about the goods provided by mountainous areas and to guide evidence-based decisions.		The Policy Briefs can be used for further research on drivers and barriers identified in the VC clusters	The Policy Briefs will report the main messages to the society	These Policy Briefs will collect and communicate the main outcomes of the comparative assessment and critical benchmarking of the VC clusters (e.g., success and failure factors).
D6.3 Synthesis report, including a		Synthesis report on strategic options. Based on the results of the regional,	Creation of innovative ventures aimed at	Creation of research projects to deepen the strategic options	Awareness raising in the international level.	Creation of international policies to manage the

Repertoire of Strategic Options	ORIGIN	cross-regional and European exercises, a synthesis report will be carried out to provide a comparative overview of all scenarios and a Repertoire of Strategic Options (possible responses of the stakeholders to tackle the challenges).	assisting value chains in adapting to new challenges, based on the strategic options.	Teaching in universities of possible future scenarios.		effects of the foresight.
D7.1 Policy Roadmap including the results of the Policy Audit and recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe's mountain areas	HighClerc Consulting	Attractive and easy-to-read policy document presenting a clear strategic perspective (with priorities and timeline) on modern policies for mountain areas that takes full account of their diverse context and multi-level governance		Raising awareness and deepening understanding of key policy issues amongst academics		Direct influence upon policy-making processes and decisions (at all relevant levels of governance) regarding the "next generation" of policy interventions for enhancing the connectivity, sustainability and resilience of mountain regions.
D7.2 Policy Design Toolkit	HighClerc Consulting	Attractive and easy-to-read policy document presenting a range of 'quick start' tools designed to promote an adaptive and reflexive approach to future policymaking for mountain areas.		Raising awareness and deepening understanding of relevant policy tools amongst academics		

Source: MOVING H2020

4.6. Lessons learned and recommendations

This section outlines the main lessons learned and recommendations drawn from the exercise and process organised in the framework of this deliverable.

4.6.1. Lessons learned

Lessons learned represent the knowledge gained during the project development. The review of lessons learned - both positive and negative - identified positive aspects to be reinforced, challenges and bottlenecks to be reconsidered and improvements needed. From the analysis carried out, it is determined that MOVING's communication and dissemination activities are on the right track to achieve its objectives and expected impact.

The following aspects of communication and dissemination tasks have been outlined as **strengths** of the project so far:

Implementation, strategy and content:

- Really strong, experienced and active team leading communication activities. AEIDL is very supportive and it shows an optimistic attitude in communication and dissemination.
- Very active communication. Good coordination among partners and personal communication.
- Multifaceted approach, well structured, organised, guided and focused.
- Communication is consistent in form.
- Concise information and visually appealing.
- Use of clear and simple messages targeting the right audience.

Communication channels:

- There is a good and regular use of social media in the project.
- There is a continuous update of channels.
- Very active social media presence.
- Well-designed project website.
- The newsletters combine project information with other news from European and international organisations and other projects.
- The VRE is found to be useful for internal communication and as a repository of documentation.

Communication products:

- MOVING has produced a wide range of communication and dissemination materials to communicate about its outcomes and results. Each of these products has a different layout and language according to the target audience.

- Availability of communication materials. Possibility to print translated communication materials for promotion.
- Newsletter and blogs (especially video blogs) are a great means of communication.
- Attractive visuals, videos, infographics and photos are used.
- Usefulness of tools developed such as Communication monitoring tool and Monitoring and Evaluation tool for regional MAPs.

Engagement and networking:

- Constant involvement of partners and encouragement to contribute to news item and blog articles and other activities.
- Organisation of knowledge exchanges events.
- Continued contact with other organisations and projects through EU MAP

Training and guidance:

- Trainings and guidance documents provided to the partners are considered useful, in particular the communication guidelines.

The exercise and analysis carried out have helped to also identify some **weaknesses and challenges** that will require the implementation of specific actions to improve in the future. These are presented hereunder:

Communication strategy:

- There is a language barrier with English.
- Communicate complex terminology and research results into an easy language, useful and understandable for local actors.
- Need to translate results to specific audiences.
- Further tailor the project communication products to each stakeholder target audience.
- Reaching people who are interest in the topic to be part of the Multi-Actor Platforms.
- Information overload. Sometimes hard to know what to prioritise as so much communication materials are produced.

Communication channels and products:

- Need for more videos and visuals linked to regional stakeholders.

Communication content:

- Communicate concrete results in a useful way for value chain practitioners and local MAP members.
- To know what information can be shared from deliverables.
- Need for more information related to local stakeholders.
- Need for more synthesis of results.
- Connect the results of the EU MAP with local stakeholders.

- Promote the area through the project.
- Find the way to communicate about key messages.

Resources:

- Lack of time. Timely production of communication items.
- Some partners lack of specific communication skills, knowledge and experience to engage further in communication and dissemination activities.

Networking and engagement:

- Involvement of regional MAPs in the EU MAP due to the difficult terminology.
- Not all local actors have e-mails or social media accounts.
- Build bridges between the world of research and politics and civil society.
- Need for more face-to-face meeting/forums with MOVING partners.
- Increase involvement of partners in creation of communication materials. There might be scope to increase the involvement of MAPs in communication and dissemination.

Training and guidance:

- Support and tips to write news and articles.
- Advice to fill the MOVING monitoring tool for communication activities.
- Understand the MOVING communication material package available.
- Support and tips to use the templates.
- Need for more instructions on how to use social media channels.

4.6.2. Recommendations

The appraisal exercise linked to this deliverable has the ultimate purpose of identifying improvements in the DECO activities and tasks to make them the most appropriate to the needs of the project. Based on the experiences in the implementation of communication and dissemination activities so far, it also provides valuable inputs to prepare the next periodic technical report. A series of recommendations have been deduced from the challenges and areas for improvement identified:

Communication strategy:

- Disseminate locally the English version of documents, newsletter, etc. does not have the same result as if it were in the national language. More communication in native languages (posts, specific translations) is needed. Encourage involvement of partners for translating content into their own languages.
- Transform the complexity of our message, terminology and results into an easy language, understandable for all type of actors.
- Share more regularly and provide more communication inputs from regional MAPs to AEIDL (WP1).
- Strengthen targeted communication to reach the most appropriate audience.

- To have more specific and more policy-oriented position papers.
- Define efficient and easy procedures to increase the engagement of partners to amplify the outreach of project results and engage the main actors.
- Enhance and incentivise the use of the DECO Monitoring tool by all partners through raising awareness about its importance to the project – e.g. capture all the information and activities performed by the partners and communicate them widely.

Communication channels and products:

- Increase communication delivered in the form of a video, story, or testimonial from members of the regional MAPs.
- Share more photos on Instagram, and other social media, during the field interviews.
- Present results by public YouTube live streaming conferences.

Engagement and networking:

- Engage young people in the regional MAPs.
- Strengthen the presence of women in regional MAPs.
- Involvement of MAP members and other involved stakeholders in communication activities, e.g. through short videos.
- Involvement of partners in creating posts about the project in their own languages (e.g. posts about meetings with MAPs, field activities).
- Find the way to compensate the involvement of MAPs members.

Training and guidance:

- Need for more instructions on how to use social media channels.
- Training from WPs leaders to the communication task force to disseminate results.
- Training on stakeholder mapping.
- Identification and presentation of good practices.
- Support and tips to write news and articles.
- Advice to fill the MOVING monitoring tool for communication activities.
- Understand the MOVING communication material package available.
- Support and tips to use the templates.

AEIDL, as leader of WP1 on Integrating research with Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach activities, will coordinate the work with the rest of partner and through the Communication Task Force, to ensure actions points are agreed and implemented by the project for the period M24-48.

4.7. Review of the contingency plan within the DECO Strategy

A first version of the contingency plan related to communication was included in the DECO Strategy taking into account the COVID-19 pandemic, leveraging the lessons learnt on how to effectively communicate during the restrictive period. Therefore, main activities included in the strategy were planned to be online, taking into account the limitations imposed by the pandemic at the time of project approval.

A list of potential risks for implementation of communication and dissemination activities was developed, together with contingency measures to mitigate their effects.

The plan is implemented and monitored by the communication team, in close relation to the lead coordinator. It feeds into the project’s reporting duties and ensures that proper and immediate follow-up steps are taken to mitigate or solve the issue.

In addition, other risks for implementation were included in the DoA linked to WP1. Table 15 presents an updated version of the risks for implementation and mitigation measures related to WP1 and the DECO Strategy.

Table 15. Risks for implementation and mitigation measures

Risk for implementation	Level of risk	Risk-mitigation measure	Additional comments
Lack of interest from public bodies and policy-makers	Low	An important exercise for identification of local authorities and policy-makers interested and active in fostering the development of mountain areas has been carried out during the proposal preparation. See annexed letters of interest. This networking activity will be a priority during the whole life of the project.	According to the high number of policy makers already involved in the project in RP1, the level of risk is modified from medium to low.
Research results are too complex to be communicated	Medium	A specific working group ('Communication Taskforce') is set up to coordinate communications efforts between the different communication departments involved. The communication leader will interact with researchers to identify the main messages. Templates for practice abstracts and policy briefs will be developed. Videos, webinars, and other products will be developed by communications experts. Communication experts have proven experience in	This risk remains evident. The proposed mitigation measure will continue to be implemented to reduce this risk from medium to low.

		disseminating complex results to society. Results will be co-developed using science-society-policy approaches.	
Project fails to meet the target KPI values for communication and dissemination	Low	Partners will establish SMART target values for the different KPIs developed. Previous agreements with local-national mass media to promote TV reports in specialised shows, magazines, newscast report, etc. Most partners have specific dissemination units well connected with media and with proved expertise in disseminating science to society.	In reporting period 1 (up to M18) the KPIs have been exceeded.
Face-to-face activities are not allowed during the project's lifespan	Low	Move the activities to an online environment, making sure proper facilitation is ensured for interactive activities such as online workshops and meetings of the CoP.	Given the new pandemic situation, regional MAPs are starting to have face-to-face activities. This is expected to continue in the coming years. The level of risk is modified from medium to low.
Target audiences have limited access to internet resources	Medium	All the MOVING communication outputs will be centralised and accessible (e.g., webinars will be recorded so stakeholders can access them at any given time, and not only during the broadcast timeframe). Internal communication between the Communication Coordinator and the Communication Group will be continuous, to exploit the connection that partners have with local communities. Relations with traditional media at regional and national levels will be reinforced, coordinated by the Communication Coordinator and implemented through the different partners.	The proposed mitigation measure will continue to be implemented to reduce this risk from medium to low.

<p>COVID-19 mitigation measures cause delay in the project implementation</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>In case the expected outcomes of the project have to be delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Strategy is flexible enough so that the communication activities can be postponed so to effectively reach target audiences.</p>	<p>Given the new pandemic situation the risk remains low. This is expected to continue in the coming years.</p>
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Source: MOVING H2020

4.8. Annex I. Key survey results

The purpose of the survey was to contribute to this self-assessment exercise by complementing the quantitative information collected in the analysis of key results progress towards achieving objectives. This survey consisted of seven sections:

- Section 1: General information
- Section 2: MOVING communication and dissemination
- Section 3: MOVING communication channels
- Section 4: MOVING communication products
- Section 5: Partners' communication actions
- Section 6: Trainings and guidelines
- Section 7: Key Exploitable Results (KER)
- Section 8: General remarks

The survey was targeted to the projects' partners, especially the communication's task force, and its results have been used to collect information to better understand: how partners are using the communication channels and products of the project, in which areas they would need further support, what challenges do they find to communicate about the project, etc.

A total of 23 responses from 21 partners have been received during April 2022.

This annex includes the analysis of the main results of the survey. Some of the results obtained have been integrated throughout the deliverable in the corresponding section.

Section 2: MOVING communication and dissemination

Partners were consulted how would qualify the communication and dissemination activities conducted by the project so far. It was asked to rate a series of statements linked to communication and dissemination activities from 1 to 4, being 1 do not agree and 4 fully agree, and giving the option of not applicable. All statements were rated between 3.2 and 3.9 scores. The scores for each of them in order of most highly rated are:

- MOVING messages are clearly conveyed (3.9 scores)
- Communicates about and amplify project results (3.8 scores)
- Useful and facilitates the understanding of project results/content (3.7 scores)
- Relevant and targeted to audiences (3.7 scores)
- Contributes to achieving the project's objectives (3.7 scores)
- Encourage and support the exchange of information, innovation, research and knowledge in the field of policies relevant to EU mountain areas (3.6 scores)
- Create a general understanding of the importance actively formulating policy options (3.6 scores)
- Help set the direction for the future mountains research agenda (3.4 scores)
- Help to build a long-lasting collective awareness on the future of mountains policies (3.2 scores)

Section 3: MOVING communication channels

The MOVING communication channels are selected to convey the key messages and outcomes of the project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target group members. The project implements a series of communication and dissemination channels to reach different kinds of final target audiences identified.

Partners were asked about the usefulness and relevance of MOVING communication channels directly for them as project partners. The rates were from 1 to 4, being 1 not useful and 4 very useful (see figure 1). The most useful channels are: MOVING website (3.7 scores), MOVING Virtual Research Environment (3.7 scores), MOVING newsletter (3.4 scores) followed by MOVING Community of Practice (CoP) (3.3 scores) and MOVING Social Media accounts (3.1 scores) (N=23).

Figure 1. Relevance of MOVING communication channels for partners

The partners were requested about the usefulness and relevance of MOVING communication channels in this case for its stakeholders (e.g. Multi-Actor Platforms actors, organisation, network, other organisations, etc). The values assigned to the utility of the channels for the partners' stakeholders are little lower than in the previous question regarding the usefulness directly for the partners (see figure 2). Using the same scale, the most useful channels for partners' stakeholders are MOVING website (3.2 scores), MOVING Social Media accounts (3.1 scores), MOVING newsletter (2.9 scores) followed by MOVING Community of Practice (CoP) (2.9 scores) and MOVING Virtual Research Environment (1.9 scores) (N=23).

Figure 2. Relevance of MOVING communication channels for stakeholders

About MOVING communication channels, the partners were asked how often share the information available on the MOVING communication channels with their network / Multi-Actor Platforms stakeholders. The 35% responded “always” or “often” and 65% answered or “sometimes” or “few times”.

Partners were also asked about the main communication channels used to inform about the results from partners’ work and MOVING with stakeholders (e.g. Multi-Actors Platforms actors, organisation, network, other organisations, etc) (see figure 3 where N=22). In this respect, indicating multi-choice responses, the 64% of the partners selected “Workshops and events organised by my organisation”, 59% “Email” followed by “Social Media accounts of my organisation” (45.5% of respondents). The “Website of my organisation” (27% of respondents) the “Newsletter of my organisation” and “Personal social media accounts” was selected by 23% of respondents. The 18% of respondents selected “Other” and specified examples such as: General assemblies, Whatsapp groups, regional newspapers and personal meetings.

Figure 3. Main communication channels used to inform about the results from partners’ work and MOVING with stakeholders

Section 4: MOVING communication products

Based on their experience and knowledge, the partners were requested to rate what is the type of information that them, and their stakeholders (e.g. Multi-Actor Platforms actors, organisation, network, other organisations, etc.) find more relevant. The rates were from 1 to 4, being 1 not relevant and 4 very relevant. Regarding the type of information consulted, the rates were (N=23): 3.5 scores to MOVING and its results; 3.5 scores to events; 3.2 scores for information

related to other EU or international organisations or stakeholders working on the sustainability of mountain regions and 2.7 scores to information related to other Horizon 2020 projects, or projects funded by other EU programmes, working on similar topics.

Figure 4. Relevance of the type of information for partners and stakeholders

Also, based on the partners experience and knowledge, it was consulted about the usefulness of MOVING communication products to be informed about the main outcomes from the project. Although all formats were highly appreciated (rated from 3.2 to 3.6 scores), the maximum values were for infographics, individual policy briefs and videos.

Figure 5. The usefulness of MOVING communication materials to inform about the main outcomes from the project

Section 5: Partners' communication actions

Partners were asked to indicate which of the following communication and dissemination actions have undertaken. Figure 6 shows the share of respondents in percentage (N=23) who have marked the type of action conducted. More than 60% answered that:

- Share the deliverables, infographics, policy briefs, videos, leaflets, and other relevant outputs produced by the project with my contacts (via email, social media, etc.) (74% of respondents).
- Translate specific outputs from the project to facilitate dissemination in my country (65% of respondents).
- Retweet or share the posts from MOVING social media accounts with my personal accounts / the accounts of my institution (61% of respondents).

Figure 6. Communication and dissemination actions conducted by MOVING partners

Some partners indicated additional communication and dissemination actions that they have carried out such as present and promote MOVING project in General assemblies, with colleagues from other similar projects, and specific thematic events; create communication materials such a roll-up; communicate about the project with social media accounts and groups created for the project in national languages; share relevant information about MOVING with regional stakeholders and other relevant authorities; communicate about the project using the newsletter of the organisation and write press releases about MOVING meetings.

In addition, the partners were asked how often share relevant information about their work in MOVING, or related to it. The 22% said “More than once a month”; 30% “Up to once a month”; 48% “Every few months” and 0% “Never”.

4.9. Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post

MOVING

- MOVING progress and results: this category refers to all posts including general updates and news about the project (e.g. consortium meetings, new sections of the website available, deliverables published)
- MOVING COP and MAPs: this category refers to all posts regarding activities of the MOVING Multi-Actor Platforms, both at regional and the EU MAP, as well as the Community in Practice.

External to MOVING:

- Other EU projects: this category refers to all posts that reference another Horizon 2020 project, or projects funded under different programmes, that are working on similar topics
- Other stakeholders: this category refers to all posts including information about the European institutions and linked networks (e.g. EC, CoR), other key EU players (e.g. ENRD, Euromontana, RUMRA), and international organisations (e.g. OECD, FAO, UN).

4.10. Annex III. Resources on evaluation of communication

- European Commission Communicating and promoting your project https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grantmanagement/communication_en.htm
- European Commission (2017). Toolkit: evaluating communication activities https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/communication-evaluation-toolkit_en.pdf
- European Commission (2019) Supporting guidance. Communication network indicators. https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/communication_network_indicators_supporting_guide.pdf
- European Commission (2019) Supporting guidance. Communication network indicators. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/informing/webinar/ec_common_set_indicators.pdf
- M. Assante, L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, L. Frosini, L. Lelli, F. Mangiacrapa, P. Pagano, G. Panichi, F. Sinibaldi, Enacting open science by D4Science, Future Generation Computer System (2019a) DOI: [10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063)
- M. Assante et al. (2019b) The gCube system: Delivering Virtual Research Environments as-a-Service. Future Gener. Comput. Syst. 95: 445-453 DOI: [10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035)